

Exploring Democracy and the Election Process in India

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Abstract

Democracy relies heavily on free and fair elections, making the electoral system a vital component of its success. This paper explores the functioning of democracy in India through its electoral system. It begins by discussing various types of democracy and how democracy is measured globally, before turning to the specific role of electoral systems in India. The paper examines the structure of election administration in India, detailing the stages of the election process from preparation to post-election activities. It also highlights the voting methods used in the country and evaluates the challenges faced, such as voter inclusivity, security, and efficiency. By studying the Indian election system, this research underscores its significance in supporting the world's largest democracy and suggests potential reforms to make elections more inclusive, transparent, and efficient.

Keywords: Democracy, Electoral Systems, Indian Elections, Election Process, Voting Methods, Electoral Reforms, Election Administration, Democratic Governance

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper explores various aspects of democracy, including its different types and measurements, with a particular focus on the election process in India. Democracy, as a political system, is

fundamentally linked to the concept of free and fair elections, which ensure representation and accountability. The paper examines how elections function in India, one of the world's largest democracies, and discusses the processes involved in conducting elections, from preparation to the actual voting phase. While extensive research exists on democracy and elections globally, limited studies have focused on the intricacies of India's election process and its alignment with democratic values. Important areas such as the administrative structure of elections and the challenges associated with modern voting methods in India have not been fully explored. This paper seeks to fill this gap by providing an in-depth analysis of India's election process, highlighting its strengths and identifying areas for reform. By focusing on the specific dynamics of India's election system, this paper contributes to the broader discussion on enhancing democratic governance and ensuring more inclusive, transparent, and efficient elections.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a qualitative research design to analyze the relationship between democracy and elections, with a particular focus on the Indian context. It examines India's democratic framework, exploring its historical evolution, institutional structures, and the role of elections in sustaining democratic values. The research relies on secondary data sources, including government reports, academic literature, statistical data, and

legislative documents, with a special emphasis on publications from the Election Commission of India. Although the research is based on secondary data and specifically examines the Indian context, it offers valuable insights into India's democratic practices and contributes to broader global discussions on improving democratic governance and election-related processes.

III. PROPOSED WORK

The proposed work is divided into two key sections: democracy and the election process in India. Each section aims to provide a deep understanding of these critical components and how they contribute to the democratic framework in India. The first section focuses on democracy, exploring its core principles, different types, and the essential role it plays in ensuring representation, equality, and accountability within a society. It also discusses the measurement of democracy, emphasizing global indicators and their specific relevance to India's democratic practices and challenges. The second section examines the election process in India, analyzing its structure and administration. It delves into the various stages involved in conducting elections, such as pre-election preparations, election day activities, and post-election procedures. This part highlights the administrative bodies responsible for managing elections, efficiency of the election process in India. This structured approach provides a holistic understanding of India's democratic framework and the election process that supports it.

A. DEMOCRACY

The first democracy was established 2500 years ago by Ancient Greeks. Two thousand five hundred years of democracy were celebrated in 1992 worldwide. The word "Democracy" was coined in Greek with the combined meaning of two words: Demos and Kratos. The meaning of demos is "The People," and the meaning of Kratos is "Strength." The power of executing government functions is distributed among a group of people; this group of people is elected by the voting process using election rules for a specific period. A very popular definition of democracy is "Government of the people, by the people and for the people," given by

Abraham Lincoln in 1863 at the place of Gettysburg. Different aspects are associated with democracy, such as social, political, economic, freedom, liberalism, equality, autonomy, etc. Democracy is also called a type of government where the representative of the people rules.

As time changes, other supportive words are attached to understand the precise meaning of democracy. There is no single definition of democracy; different authors defined democracy in their own words. Some authors described: "Democracy is a form of government in which the people, either directly or indirectly, take part in governing". Sultana wrote in his paper that "democracy is a system in which political power is transferred through an election held at regular intervals, and people choose their representatives from two or more political parties" (Sultana T., 2012a, p.38).

Four key elements were given by Larry Diamond (2006) while describing democracy in the lecture. According to the author, these elements are: i) Free and fair elections should be conducted for replacing and choosing the rules, ii) There should be high and interactive participation of citizens in different aspects, iii) Human Rights should be protected, and iv) Application of laws and procedures should be executed on all people without any discrimination (Diamond, L. Jay., & Plattner, M. F., 2006; Nwogu, 2015).

Types of Democracy: Many countries have adopted democracy, and every country has tried to show that there is more political participation in their country with equality, freedom, liberalism, etc., which are inspiring ideas and suitable for their nations. The method of political participation varies in many countries, and due to this, many forms of democracy have come to exist. However, each form of democracy must not demolish the basic idea of democracy, such as the participation of eligible citizens, discussion and debates, making laws and policies and their implementations, the judiciary system, etc. The various stakeholders differentiate democracy based on the nature of government and representation. The most known types of democracy are listed below (Sultana T., 2012b, p.33; Saylor Academy, n.d.):

Figure 1: Different Types of Democracy

For better understanding and clearly, the above-listed different forms of democracy are explained below:

i) **Direct Democracy:** It is a fundamental and pure form of democracy. Citizens participate directly in the whole process of decision-making. Every person has an equal chance to participate in policymaking in direct democracy. It is suitable and effective where political units are small and unsuitable for large nations. Direct democracy is also used for referendum because individuals participate personally, speak, and express their thoughts. International Institute of Democracy and Electoral Assistance (IDEA) analyzed four forms of democracy which are described below (Virginia B., et al., 2008):

- a) Recall
- b) Agenda Initiatives
- c) Citizens Initiatives and
- d) Referendum

a) **Recall:** Recall is used to end the officiating person's tenure or to remove them from their chair for working continuously. Voting takes place to remove an elected person from office. The required number of signatures is collected; this is the process of recall.

b) **Agenda Initiatives:** In this form, there is an agenda of either a legislative assembly or parliament assembly on a specific topic, and people raise issues on this agenda. Agenda initiatives can be applied at both state and national levels. Procedures and rules vary from country to country to bring this initiative.

c) **Citizens Initiatives:** People can vote for different aspects like constitutional,

political, legislative, etc. Supporters must have enough written approvals for initiatives of the proposal regarding constitutional procedures, acts, etc., according to jurisdiction.

d) **Referendum:** Direct voting is included in referendum procedures on particular issues like legislative issues, constitutional issues, political issues, etc. Voting in referendums is allowed only when the competent authority decides it according to legal processes and rules. In exceptional cases, the referendum is permitted when it is demanded by a specific community or citizens on sensitive issues.

ii) **Representative Democracy:** It is also called indirect democracy. Representative democracy is also called indirect democracy because, in this form, people do not directly participate in decision-making and other political participation; they choose their representative for a specific tenure. These representatives are selected for the local and national levels to form the government. Citizens' power is transferred to these elected representatives (Sultana T., 2012a, p.33). According to the author Shukla, Representative democracy is a kind of limited democracy because they are chosen for a limited period. After completion, voting is required for re-electing the same or another representative of the people. The key points of representative democracy are:

- Representative democracy is successful because it is practically possible. After all, the participation of the whole population in the governing process is not feasible.
- It makes it easy for an inexperienced ordinary person to handle different kinds of political, social, policy making, law and order, economic, governing work, etc.

- Representative democracy is suitable for keeping stability.

Political Liberty, Political equality, and sovereignty are fundamental principles of representative democracy ("Democracy", 2017).

Representative democracy can be further categorized as Parliamentary, Presidential and mixed systems. These are based on the division of powers and type of electoral procedure and are briefly discussed below (Saylor Academy, n.d.).

- a) Parliamentary system
- b) Presidential system
- c) Mixed system

a) Parliamentary system: Most democratic countries use the parliamentary system or form of democracy. Because powers are under the control of the legislative division of the system, the legislature has a fixed number of seats for representatives, elected from different geographical areas of the nation by citizens. A political party or a collaborative group of parties that has a large number of representatives is declared as a winning party. It selects its governing head, called the head of the state or the Prime Minister of the state. The head of the government is responsible for controlling legislative activities. Executive powers of different branches of government are divided among other members of the Parliament. The electoral system of Parliament varies from country to country.

b) Presidential System: The Presidential system differs from the parliamentary system in many ways. The judiciary, executive, and legislative are parts of government that are independent of each other. The executives and the legislative members can be elected simultaneously by voters. The head of the executive

branch is the head of the state or government and is called the President. The legislative branch does not influence the executive branch. Powers are detached from the legislative to the executive branch. The President is responsible for all government activities. Presidents made necessary executive appointments.

c) Mixed System: This form of democracy is a mix of parliamentary and presidential systems. This is also called the semi-presidential system. This mixed system has both types of characteristics.

iii) Deliberative Democracy: The word "Deliberative democracy" was used by Joseph M. Bessette in 1980. Deliberative democracy is a form of democracy in which a decision is based on a discussion. Sometimes, it is also seen as a combined version of representative and direct democracy. Binachi, defined Deliberative Democracy in 2008. It can be understood with four principles:

- **Reciprocity:** People should be involved in public issues.
- **Publicity:** Nothing should be hidden.
- **Accountability:** Responsibility for decisions taken.
- **Inclusion:** All views, thoughts, and interests of members should be considered in deliberation (Bianchi G., 2008).

iv) Liberal Democracy: The execution powers of government are according to the constitution in Liberal Democracy and protect the rights of humans, freedoms, and minorities. A democracy that protects citizens' rights, freedoms, facilities, etc., is usually called Liberal democracy (Sultana T., 2012b).

v) Guided Democracy: Guided democracy is known as directed democracy and is also

known as managed democracy. In this type of democracy, elections are controlled by the government. The working methods of the government are similar to despotism but show a representative democracy. Citizens are not fully allowed to participate in political participation because it is managed that they are not for this.

vi) **Social Democracy:** The term social democracy was attached to the 19th century. Social democracy is based on equality among citizens. Equality should be present in each field, including freedom, economic, social, political, health, education, etc., with social justice. It also forces redistribution, similar to Marxism, for liberal representative democracy. Accordingly, all sources should be equally utilized and distributed among people for social welfare ("Elections", 2017).

- Electoral system
- Disproportionality
- The effective number of parties
- Political participation

Swedish Research Institute (V-Dem) Variety of Democracy published a report based on the measurement of democracy type. Electoral democracy, Liberal Democracy, Participatory Democracy, Deliberative Democracy, and Egalitarian Democracy are considered for this. The Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) also publishes an index on democracy. It includes Full democracy, Flawed Democracy, Hybrid Regimes, and Authority Regimes with different factors and categories. The Polity Data series is also the most used in political science research. The origin of the polity Data Series is US-based (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2021a, p.2; Geissel, Kneuer, & Lauth, 2016; Fuchs & Roller, 2018; Högström J., 2011).

Measurement of Democracy: Most countries are democratic countries worldwide, and different types of electoral processes and democracy are used. It is a complicated task to measure the quality of democracy among countries with many varieties. Many institutes, organizations, scholars, etc., publish ranks and indexes of democratic countries based on various and different criteria. The number of groups of other variables is made with a scaling point system, uses statistical methods, and generates or assigns a rank to specific countries. Organizations that publish reports regarding democracy annually are Variety of Democracy (V-Dem Institute), Democracy Index, Polity Data Series, MaxRange, etc. A total of more than 65 variables are there which are used to measurement of democracy. A few of them are listed below:

- Population
- Political institutions
- Socioeconomic equality
- Type of democracy
- Functioning of democracy
- Political cultural
- Geographic region
- Dominating religion
- Literacy of citizens
- Degree of democracy

Table 1: Democracy Index 2020

Rank	Country Name	Overall Score	Electoral Process	Function of Govt.	Political Participation	Political Culture	Civil Liberties
1	Norway	9.81	10.00	9.64	10.00	10.00	9.41
2	Iceland	9.37	10.00	8.57	8.89	10.00	9.41
3	Sweden	9.26	9.58	9.29	8.33	10.00	9.12
4	New Zealand	9.25	10.00	8.93	8.89	8.75	9.71
5	Canada	9.24	9.58	8.93	8.89	9.38	9.41
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11	Taiwan	8.94	10.00	9.64	7.22	8.13	9.71
12	Switzerland	8.83	9.58	8.57	7.78	9.38	8.82
13	Luxembourg	8.68	10.00	8.57	6.67	8.75	9.41
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53	India	6.61	8.67	7.14	6.67	5.00	5.59
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167	North Korea	1.08	0.00	2.50	1.67	1.25	0.00

Table 1 shows the Democracy Index 2020 according to a report by EIU with rank, country name, and overall ranking score with the division of scores. Norway holds the first rank with full

democracy, and India holds the 53rd position in indexing among 167 countries (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2021b, p.8).

B. ELECTION PROCESS

The election process is a fundamental aspect of democratic governance, allowing voters to select their representatives. It consists of all activities from the start to the end of the election, including the declaration of the result. Different phases or steps are involved in the election process. In India, articles 324 to 329 define terminology for elections and electoral systems (ECI, n.d.,-d).

1. Types of Elections held in India

Different types of elections are conducted in India, such as President elections, Vice-President elections, Lok Sabha elections, Rajya Sabha elections, State legislature elections, and others, as shown in Figure 2. These elections are conducted on the completion of their tenure.

Figure 2: Types of Elections held in India

- **President election:** The President is called the head of the state and is also the first citizen of the nation in India. Indian constitution articles 25 to 78 deal with union executives like the President, Vice-President, Prime Minister, and the Attorney Journal of India. The President is not elected directly; the electoral college elects the President. The electoral college consists of elected members of Parliament's both houses, elected members of the state legislative assemblies, and elected members of the union territories. Any nominated member of either the house of Parliament or state legislative assemblies and union

territories cannot cast a vote in the election of the President in India. The values of these votes vary according to the seats of MLA and MP.. The value of votes of an MLA and MP are different. Also, the value of a vote of an MLA of one state also differs from the value of a vote of an MLA of another state. The formula for the calculation of the value of a vote of an MLA is given below:

$$\text{Value of the Vote of an MLA} = \frac{\text{Total population of State}}{\text{Total number of elected members in the State Legislature}} \times (0.001)$$

For example: Total Population of Haryana (assumption) = 30,000,000.

Total Number of Elected Members (MLAs) in Haryana State Legislature = 90

Value of the Vote of an MLA in Haryana $(30000000 / 90) \times 0.001 = 333.33$

The total value of votes of all MLAs of one state is obtained by multiplying the value of one vote by the total number of MLAs of that state. This way, the total value of votes of MLAs of each state is calculated and used for the calculation of the value of one vote of an MP. The formula for calculation of the value of votes of an MP is given under

$$\text{Value of the Vote of an MP} = \frac{\text{Total Values of Votes of all MLAs of all states}}{\text{Total Number of Elected Members of both houses of Parliament}}$$

The value of the vote of an MP is the same for all MPs (Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha) respective of their states. The STV electoral system is used to elect the President in India. A candidate must fulfill the minimum criteria to be selected according to the electoral quota. The formula used for the electoral quota is given below:

$$\text{Electoral Quota} = \frac{\text{Total Values of Valid Votes Polled}}{2} + 1$$

To win the Presidential election, a candidate must secure more than 50% of the total votes polled. If no candidate achieves the required majority (more than 50%) in the first round of counting, a process of elimination and redistribution of votes takes place. The candidate with the fewest votes is eliminated, and their votes are transferred to the next preferred candidate on those ballots. This process continues until a candidate crosses the 50% threshold.

- **Vice-President election:** After the President, the second highest and most responsible authority is the Vice-President. The Vice-President works as a chairman of the Rajya Sabha. It is also not elected directly; the electoral college comprises nominated and elected members of both houses of Parliament only. MLAs of state are not allowed to cast their votes in election to the Vice-President. The electoral system STV is used for this election with a secret ballot. It is necessary to conduct the election of Vice-President within 60 days if the seat remains vacant for any reason. The Vice-President works in the absence of the President. (PIB, 2022; The Presidential and Vice-Presidential Elections Act, 1952, n.d.; Legislative Department, Ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India, n.d.).
- **Lok Sabha election:** Lok Sabha is also called the Lower House of Parliament in India. Voters directly choose members of the Lok Sabha. The tenure of a Lok Sabha member is five years. The FPTP electoral system is used to choose members of the Lok Sabha.
- **Rajya Sabha election:** Rajya Sabha is called the Upper house of the Indian Parliament. The tenure of the Rajya Sabha members is six years, and legislative members of the state and union territories elect these members. MPs of Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha are not allowed to cast their votes in the election to members of Rajya Sabha. Elections are held every two years for the Rajya Sabha for one-third of the

members. The STV electoral system is used to elect Rajya Sabha members through open ballots.

- **State Legislature election:** An MLA is a member of the state legislature. The tenure of the MLA is five years. The head of the MLAs becomes the Chief Minister of the state. The Chief Electoral Officer (CEO) of the state is accountable for conducting free and fair elections in the state. The number of seats varies from state to state.
- **Panchayat election:** Panchayat elections are conducted for local governments. Panchayat elections are modernized under the 73rd amendments. Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRI) includes three tier systems: i) Gram Panchayat, ii) Block Samiti, and iii) Zila Parishad. Gram Panchayat is formed for villages, Block Samiti is formed for a group of villages, and Zila Parishad elections are conducted at the level of the district. These elections are conducted after five years under the Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRI).

According to the Constitution of India (2024), any elections can be delayed due to emergencies and other technical reasons.

2. Election Process in India

In India, the parliamentary system forms the government. In this system, powers are divided between the central and state governments. Representatives of the people are elected for both central and state governments. Elections are conducted to elect these representatives in different phases; each phase includes activities. The election process includes these activities from start to end.

a) Structure of Election Administration in India

The Election Commission of India (ECI) organizes elections throughout the country. The Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) leads the ECI with the help of Election Commissioners (ECs). They manage important national elections like those for

the Lok Sabha and the President of India. In every state, there is a State Election Commission headed by a State Election Commissioner. This commission manages local elections like municipal corporations and panchayats within the state. At the district level, District Election Officers (DEOs) supervise the election process. Each constituency has a Returning Officer (RO) who manages the elections in that area. The RO is assisted by Assistant Returning Officers (AROs), who help with tasks such as checking nomination papers and setting up polling stations etc. to ensure the voting process is fair and transparent. At the lowest level, the Booth Level Officer (BLO) takes care of specific polling booth areas. They update voter lists, educate voters, verify details, and help voters during elections.

During elections in India, the polling process at each polling station is managed by the Presiding Officer (PRO), Assistant Presiding Officer (APRO), and Polling Officers (POs). They maintain order, supervise the polling process, and all activity during voting. Each person involved in the electoral process, from the CEC to the BLOs, plays an important role in elections in India (ECI, n.d.,-a).

b) Phases during Election Process in India

Different activities are involved in completing the various types of elections in India. These activities are categorized into three phases: i) the pre-election phase, ii) the polling phase, and iii) the post-election phase, as shown in Figure 3. Activities that are carried out before the polling are included in the pre-election phase, and activities that are carried out after the declaration of the result are included in the post-election phase. The remaining activities between the pre-election and post-elections are considered under the polling phase.

Figure 3: Phases of Election Process in India

Election process activities can be categorized into many forms, but all activities/steps are performed in all elections. All activities are listed below according to the model checklist of the Chief Electoral Officer (CEO), District Electoral Officer (DEO), and Returning Officer (RO) (ECI, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c).

Activities performed in the pre-election phase are:

- Awareness campaign for citizens
- Voter registration and electoral roll preparation
- Preparation and revision of electoral rolls to ensure accuracy
- Announcement of election schedule
- Implementation of the MCC to ensure ethical behavior and fair campaigning by candidates and parties
- Security arrangements and law & order preparedness
- Managing polling station
- Deputation of employees
- Arrangement of different types of training
- Managing election goods and material
- Candidate nomination
- Scrutiny of nominations
- Withdrawal of candidature
- Allotment of election symbols
- Preparation of EVM, ballot papers
- Monitoring of budget and expenditure spent by contesting candidates and parties
- Appointment of polling officers/ officials

Activities performed in the polling phase are:

- Polling booth setup
- Deployment of election officials, polling, and security personnel
- Supervision of the polling process to ensure smooth conduct and adherence to election laws
- Voting by registered voters
- Monitoring and management of polling stations to facilitate voting

Activities performed in the post-election phase are:

- Set up of counting hall
- Counting of votes cast during the election
- Declaration of election results based on the votes counted
- Handling of disputes and election petitions
- Post-election reporting and documentation
- Preparation for new government formation
- Secure storage and handling of electronic voting machines (EVMs) and other election materials
- Post-poll analysis and feedback

The different activities involved in the election listed above are performed according to the rules of the ECI (Lakxmikanth, M., 2018a; The Conduct of Elections Rules, 1961).

c) Existing Voting Methods used in India

The voting method refers to the way in which people cast their votes to elect a candidate. It includes the process and technology used during elections to record votes. In other words, it is the way, citizens participate in choosing their representatives through designated methods like marking a ballot or using electronic devices. This section focuses on existing voting methods used in India by the Election Commission of India (ECI) for different types of voters.

- **Voting by ballot paper on the polling booth:** Ballot paper voting is a paper-based voting system. In this method, the voter visits the polling station to vote, and the officials verify the voter in the booth and make a mark on the voter list with a pen/marker. Marks are put on the finger of the voter with indelible ink, and the ballot paper is issued to the voter. A ballot paper is a list of contesting candidates with a symbol printed on paper. Voters cast votes secretly in the voting compartment by marking contesting candidates and dropping the ballot paper into the ballot box. After the

poll is over, the ballot box is sealed and deposited to the Returning Officer. Many votes are treated as invalid votes due to wrong marks on the ballot paper.

- **ETPBS voting method for service voters:** ETPBS is an Electronically Transmitted Postal Ballot System. This system is used for special service voters. In this method, Unit officers are appointed in the unit of the service voter, and information about the voter is sent to the ERO through a web portal. ERO verifies those voters according to the respective constituencies. After finalizing the contesting candidates, ballot papers with secret codes and numbers and related documents are sent back to the unit officer. Service voters download their postal ballot papers through credentials and print them on paper. Service voters cast their votes and send these ballot papers by post by keeping ballot paper inside the proper covers. This received ballot is deposited in the custody of the Returning Officer for the day of counting. Each cover has a unique number that is scanned during the counting of the ballots. If the scanning code is mismatched with the existing record, it is marked as an invalid ballot.
- **Proxy voting method for classified service voters:** Proxy voting for classified service voters in India allows certain eligible individuals, such as members of the armed forces, to appoint someone else to vote on their behalf if they are unable to do so in person due to their service responsibilities. Classified service voters include military personnel, members of paramilitary forces, and government officials deployed in remote or sensitive areas. To use proxy voting, a classified service voter must appoint a proxy (another registered voter) to cast a vote on his/ her behalf. The proxy can then vote at the designated polling station on election day after showing the appointment letter and required documents. Proxy voting ensures that classified service voters have the opportunity to participate in elections even if they are unable to be

physically present at their registered constituency on polling day due to their duties.

- **Postal ballot voting method:** The postal ballot system is used for those voters who are deployed on the different duties of the election and for those public employees working in other constituencies rather than their home constituencies. Such voters send a request on a prescribed form to the concerned Returning Officer. After verifying the details mentioned on the prescribed form, a mark is made on the voter list to stop proxy voting. After the contesting candidates are finalized, ballot papers and related documents are returned to the requester. Voters cast their votes and send these ballot papers by post by keeping ballot paper inside the proper covers. These received ballots are deposited to the Returning Officer to be used on the day of counting (ECI, n.d.,-b).
- **Home voting method for elderly and PwD voters:** This kind of voting is used for senior citizens (85+) and persons with 40% benchmark disabilities. Such voters send a request on a prescribed form to their concerned Returning Officer through Booth Level Officers (BLOs). After verifying the details mentioned on the prescribed form, a mark is made on the voter list to stop proxy voting. After finalizing the contesting candidates, a special team is constituted which facilitates these voters to cast their votes. Such a team comprises of Presiding Officer, Assistant Presiding Officer, Polling Officers, Police Personnel, Videographers, etc. These teams visit the voter's home along with BLO, verify the voter, issue ballot paper, and make a temporary pooling booth at home under surveillance. The vote is cast by the voter and dropped into the ballot box. This ballot box is deposited to the Returning Officer to be used on the day of counting (ECI, n.d.,-c).
- **Voting using EVM:** EVM is an electronic voting machine. It is the replacement of

paper-based voting. The vote is cast using a machine by pressing a button in front of the candidate's name and symbol rather than dropping ballot paper in the ballot box. The rest of the process remains the same as in paper-based voting, and no vote is marked invalid. In this method, the voter visits the polling booth to vote, and the officials verify the voter in the booth and mark the voter list with a pen/ marker. Marks with indelible ink are placed on the finger of the voter, and the electronic ballot paper is issued to the voter using the control unit. A ballot unit is also an electronic machine that shows a list of contesting candidates with a symbol along with a button. Voters cast votes secretly in the voting compartment by pressing a button. After pressing a button, a beep sound is raised. After completion of all voting, seals are put in the presence of authorized persons and submitted to the strong room under surveillance, which is accessed on the day of counting.

- **EDC voting method for voters deployed on different election duties:** The EDC system is used for voters who are deployed to different duties of the election and for public employees working in their home constituencies. Such voters send a request on a prescribed form to the concerned Returning Officer. After verifying the details mentioned on the prescribed form, a mark is made on the voter list to stop proxy voting. Voters with an EDC can visit any polling booth of his/ her home constituency to cast a vote, and the voter submits an EDC to the presiding officer. The remaining process is the same as used in voting using EVM.

Above are the different voting methods used by Indian citizens to cast their votes in India. All necessary instructions are available on the official website of ECI. (ECI., 2021a, August 26; ECI., 2019).

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study examines the current state of democracy in India using the Democracy Index 2020. While India is one of the largest democracies, it still faces challenges that prevent it from reaching its full democratic potential. Countries like Norway, Iceland, and Sweden, ranked at the top, have strong democratic systems with high citizen participation, protection of rights, and well-functioning governments. India, ranked 53rd, scores lower, especially in areas like political participation and civil liberties, with a score of 5.59 for civil liberties. This indicates ongoing struggles in safeguarding the rights and freedoms of its citizens. While elections are held regularly, concerns about transparency, inclusivity, and the quality of participation still exist. The study stresses the importance of improving India's political culture, public engagement, and ensuring inclusivity in politics. To strengthen democracy, India needs to address these issues, provide better representation for marginalized groups, and improve its electoral system to make it more transparent and efficient. By addressing these challenges, India can build a more inclusive and fair democracy for all its citizens

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References- A comprehensive list of references written in APA 7th edition style.

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